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Ancient caravan routes played an important role in the development of trade, which had a basic place in the development of trade until the middle of the XIX century. These routes were significant in trade and diplomatic relations of the Central Asian khanates, and the Emirate of Bukhara took a substantial position in these routes. The city of Bukhara is at the crossroads of these roads, and the roads of communication of neighboring khanates with each other and with other countries pass through the territory of the city. For this reason, the Emirate of Bukhara was in the spotlight of Russian tourists and traders.

The role of the Emirate of Bukhara in domestic and international trade is described in the works of Russian travelers, ambassadors and traders who visited and

FOREIGN TRADE RELATIONS OF THE BUKHARA EMIRATE

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ABSTRACT

An insight provided at the article reviews of some profound investigation on the scientific basis the aspects of the role of ancient caravan routes in the development of trade relations, the importance of the Bukhara Emirate in the development of trade of these routes until the middle of the XIX century. These routes played an important role in trade and diplomatic relations of the Central Asian khanates, and the Emirate of Bukhara had a basic place in these routes. The city of Bukhara is at the crossroads of these roads, and the roads of communication of neighboring khanates with each other and with other countries pass through the territory of the city. Therefore, the Bukhara Emirate was in the spotlight of Russian travelers and traders.

traveled directly to Central Asia and the Arab countries.

In trade relations between the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, along with the caravan route, the Amudarya waterway was used, and between the Bukhara Emirate and the Kokand Khanate, a caravan passing through land and mountains. They are the main trade routes.

P.I. Nebolsin, who conducted research in the Caspian and Kazakh steppes, in his book "Description of Russia's trade with Central Asia" gives the following information: The Bukhara Emirate occupies a leading position in the foreign trade relations of the Kokand Khanate. Because of the border between the two countries, they were connected by many caravan routes. In particular, there were two large caravan

routes, along with many trails connecting the Fergana Valley, which was the central part of the Kokand Khanate, and the Bukhara Emirate. In the first, the caravan from Kokand was long to Bukhara via Besharik, Mahram, Khojand, Uratepa, Zaamin, Jizzakh, Yangikurgan and Samarkand. So the second caravan way was long from Kokand Besharik, Mahram, Khojand, Uratepa, Djom, Ravvot, Djizak, Yangikurgan and Samarkand. The first caravan route was 526 versts (Verst is a unit of length equal to 1.0668 km), while the second caravan route was 615 versts "[2-176]. Between Kokand and Bukhara, caravans reached their destination in about 20-23 days, and along with camels and horses, Kokand carts were widely used on these roads. Y.K. Meyendorf, who was in Bukhara in the 1920s., wrote "... Kokand merchants bring their goods to Bukhara by cart" [3-108]. The camel, which is the main carrier in the Kokand-Bukhara caravan, was paid from 2 to 3.75 gold coins, depending on the weather and political situation [4-142]. On the eve of the Russian invasion, there were separate caravan routes from Tashkent, one of the largest cities of the Kokand Khanate, to the cities of the Bukhara Emirate. The caravan traveled on the Tashkent-Bukhara road for 12-18 days, depending on the weather, and covered a distance of 498 versts, and on these caravan routes it was possible to use the services of camels, horses and carts. On the Bukhara-Tashkent caravan route, camels were paid up to 2.25, 2.5 and 2.75 gold coins [5-120,122].

Between the Kokand and Khiva khanates, small caravans traveled throughout the years [6-18]. They mainly used the Bukhara-Khiva caravan route, which was 340 versts from Bukhara to

Khiva, and the caravan covered this route in 10 days. Although the Kokand khanate traded with the Khiva khanate mainly through caravan routes passing through the Bukhara emirate and the emirate's markets, it also passed through Tashkent, which directly connected the two countries. There was a caravan route.

Especially, in the memoirs of Nikolai Muravyev, who was in Central Asia in 1819-1820, it is noted that the Khiva khanate was connected with Bukhara and Balkh via the Amudarya, with Tashkent and Kokand through the Syrdarya. However, due to the long river route through the Syrdarya and the lack of access for large ships, it was rarely used by traders. As a result, the Kokand-Khiva trade through the Bukhara Emirate remained important. This, in turn, shows that the Emirate of Bukhara played a decisive role in the trade of countries in the region [7-175].

Moreover, the city of Bukhara played an essential role in trade relations between the Khiva Khanate, Kokand Khanate, Afghanistan, India, Iran, Arab countries, Turkey and other countries. The distance from Bukhara to Kabul is 985 versts, and the caravan traveled on this road for 22-25 days. The distance from Kabul to Peshawar was 320 versts, 8 days. In Bukhara, the caravan had to travel 169 days, 6760 versts to reach Calcutta, the largest port city of India [7-175]. In the 1960s, traders paid 8.5 Bukhara coins for each loaded camel on the Peshawar-Bukhara route [2-121]. Marvari Barayev, who led the Orenburg expedition, gives interesting information about the trade routes of Indian traders who came to Bukhara in 1735 for trade. He traveled from Delhi to Kabul, a city on the border with India, from there to Bukhara via Badakhshan, from there to Khiva to trade

with Indian traders, and from there to Astrakhan by caravan for a month and a half. The road leading Bukhara merchants to India required a huge turn. They ascend to the Indian Ocean, where shipping was discontinued, from where goods flowed to Ghazni, India's main market, and then across Bukhara to Kandahar.

Mir Izzatulla, who was in Bukhara in 1812, noted that special caravanserais were built in Bukhara for foreign traders and they were called by different names. For example, Indians from Shikarpura traded in the Alamkhana khanakoh, while caravanserai called Nohaysaroy housed Tatar traders [8-202].

In 1820-1821, the Russian tourist Y.K. Meyendorf in his diary notes that many Muscovite, Iranian, and Indian merchants

came to Bukhara. Among them were Indian traders who brought to Bukhara a large amount of Indian dye indigo (nil), precious stones, real pearls, sugar, shiny and white thin fabrics, silk fabrics and cashmere rice [9- 169]. At the same time, Bukhara became a transit center for foreign goods to many cities in Central Asia. Particularly, Russian, Iranian and Indian goods were transported from Bukhara to Tashkent.

Based on the above facts, we can see in the works and memoirs of Russian tourists and traders and researchers detailed information about the Emirate of Bukhara, trade and communication routes in Central Asia. However, research in this area still needs to be continued.

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